

Primary Science Quiz 2025

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Event Date: 25/11/2025

Venue: Devere Hall, UCC

Event Type: Outreach Event

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Organising Committee: Mervyn Horgan,^a Mohamed Sharafeldin,^b Eric Moore,^b William Daly,^b

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Event Sponsors

Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Lifetime Lab, Old Cork Waterworks, Cork City Council

Comhairle Cathrach Chorcaí
Cork City Council

Summary

The Primary Science Quiz 2025 brought together approximately 180 primary school students from 60 Schools across Cork for an exciting and competitive science event held in the iconic UCC Devere Hall, renowned as the venue for UCC's annual graduation ceremonies. Teams participating were selected after internal competitions at schools' level (approximately 3-5 teams/school). The event opened with words of thanks to the organisers and sponsors, setting a celebratory and welcoming tone for the day. Students competed in eight quiz rounds, each consisting of eight questions, with all questions read aloud by the event moderator and simultaneously projected on the hall screen. Teams were given an additional one minute at the end of each round before answer sheets were collected.

A dedicated team of volunteers from the School of Chemistry and Lifetime Labs played a crucial role throughout the event, helping to organise teams, proctor students, distribute materials, and collect answer sheets. A midway break provided refreshments for participants, including biscuits and juice, while parents and guardians were offered tea, coffee, and biscuits. The event included raffle and spot prizes and concluded with a prize-giving to the five highest-scoring

teams, presented by the Deputy Lord Mayor. To recognise their enthusiasm and participation, every child who competed received a participation medal.

Attendees

Approximately 150 primary schools' students, equally distributed (male/females).

Target audience: School students.

Prizes

Cloghroe National School were the overall winners.

Figure 1. Overall Winners, Cloghroe National School, celebrating their trophy with participants and parents/guardians.

Photos

Various participating teams are pictured below. All students have signed and agreed for their photos to be shared. **Photo credit:** Clare Keogh.

Feedback

Deputy Lord Mayor Cllr. Margaret McDonnell commented “The hard work by the all the children participating and the important role of parents and teachers in the lead up to the event must be acknowledged and it looks like our future is in good hands”. On the importance of STEM Cllr. McDonnell stated “there has never been a better time to study science as there are a wide range of interesting and rewarding opportunities in this industry with many more exciting roles to emerge in the coming years”

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Royal Society of Chemistry Republic of Ireland Local Section, Lifetime Lab, Old Cork Waterworks, and Cork City Council, for funding and supporting this event.

Previous Events in this Series

Primary Science Quiz 2024, 13th November 2024
[\(https://www.corkcity.ie/en/old-cork-waterworks-experience/news/primary-science-quiz-2024/\)](https://www.corkcity.ie/en/old-cork-waterworks-experience/news/primary-science-quiz-2024/)
 Primary Science Quiz 2023, 21st November 2023,
[\(https://www.corkcity.ie/en/old-cork-waterworks-experience/news/cloghroe-ns-win-2023-primary-science-quiz/\)](https://www.corkcity.ie/en/old-cork-waterworks-experience/news/cloghroe-ns-win-2023-primary-science-quiz/)
 Primary Science Quiz 2022, 16th November 2022,
[\(https://www.corkcity.ie/en/old-cork-waterworks-experience/news/primary-science-quiz-a-huge-success/\)](https://www.corkcity.ie/en/old-cork-waterworks-experience/news/primary-science-quiz-a-huge-success/)